

Striking polymorphism among infertile helpers in the arboreal ant *Gesomyrmex*

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APPENDIX Electronic Supplementary Material

Fig. S1 Entrance of *Gesomyrmex* sp. nest G and inhabited chamber (4cm long; 0.3cm wide) (Thailand colony).

Fig. S2 Use of a saw attached to a bamboo pole to collect nests of *Gesomyrmex* sp. in dry evergreen forest (Loei province, Thailand).

Fig. S3 Adults and brood inside the Sabah nest of *Gesomyrmex* sp. Bottom photos show the inhabited chamber inside a small branch.

Fig. S4 SEMs of worker (above) and soldier (below) heads in *Gesomyrmex* sp. (Thailand colony). The “spiky” setae on mandibles and clypeus are absent in worker and present in soldier.

Fig. S5 Thorax differences among workers, soldiers and queens (shown at different scales) of *Gesomyrmex* sp. (Sabah colony). Queen thorax of *Oecophylla smaragdina* is shown for comparison (AntWeb CASENT0173644).

Fig. S6 *Gesomyrmex* sp. worker retrieving a fly (superfamily Sciaroidea) in Virachey National Park, Cambodia.

Fig. S7 Traces of red dye inside gasters of soldier and workers of *Gesomyrmex* sp. (Thailand colony, nest E).

Fig. S8 *Gesomyrmex* sp. supersoldier with swollen gaster (Sabah colony). Dissection (specimen preserved in ethanol) showed 8 ovarioles and presence of 2 large yolky oocytes.

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